

EGGER Group

Cascading wood use

EGGER produces an extensive product range of wood-based materials based on chipboard, OSB, and MDF board, as well as timber.

Highlights of innovative features

- In Romania, EGGER commissioned both a recycling facility at the production plant and public waste wood collection points to enable local waste wood flows.
- The waste wood is shredded before transport to the production plant to reduce the number of transporting trucks.
- Instead of releasing emissions, around 3.1 tons of CO² are bound in each recycled ton of waste wood.
- The quantities of waste wood recycled by EGGER in Romania in 2019 replaced the potential use of approx. 65,900 ha of forest.

For the production of wood-based materials, EGGER invests in resource saving technology and uses not only primary but also secondary, i.e. recycled raw materials. Cascading wood reduces the need for fresh roundwood and prolongates the carbon capture. Using recycling material in the production of chipboards is a prime case for Circular Economy in the sector.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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